

Modern methods of investigation of morphofunctional characteristics of the cardiovascular system in children

Шавдирова Гулбону Мансуровна

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It is difficult to overestimate the importance of ultrasound diagnostics in modern medical practice. With the help of modern technology it has become possible to non-invasively see the heart itself, its structure, its work. The method of echocardiography makes it possible to present real-time information on all basic characteristics of the heart: morphology, kinetics of individual structures and the heart as a whole; as well as to assess the hemodynamic state. All previous methods to study the cardiovascular system: phonocardiography, radiography, phase analysis, other noninvasive and invasive techniques solved the problem each in its own limits. Electrocardiography carries a large stratum of information. But this technique characterizes only electrical phenomena in the heart. It can't be used to establish anatomical features precisely, to characterize myocardial contractile function state confidently. Echocardiography can tell about all this objectively. Currently, there is a fairly acceptable system of cardiac imaging standards from different accesses during different phases of its activity.

Modern echocardiographic equipment provides high-quality visualization of cardiac structures, allows detailed characterization of intracardiac hemodynamics, contractile, pumping and relaxation parameters of the heart.

There are currently the following types of cardiac echolocation: B, 2D, M, D, and

Doppler method. Image during B-mode scanning is obtained due to the fact that each beam coming from the transducer meets obstacles on its way; then information about the depth of each obstacle is transferred to the screen, and the image of the object, dissected by the ultrasound plane, is formed from a set of points. The image in this case is not only a copy of the real object, but synchronously duplicates all its movements. Therefore, in the literature this mode is called two-dimensional echocardiography in real time. M-mode is a time sweep of a single beam and thus represents a variant of the one-dimensional technique. In M-mode, the vertical axis on the echocardiograph screen represents the distance from the heart structures to the transducer, and the horizontal axis represents the time. The M-mode provides an objective view of the movement of various heart structures that are crossed by a single ultrasound beam.

The special effect of sound reflection was discovered by Christian Johannes Doppler in 1842. In 1961 D.Franclin first reported the application of the Doppler effect to study blood flow. Clinical use of the Doppler method in cardiology began in the 80's. As applied to cardiology, the Doppler effect consists in the fact that when ultrasound signal is reflected from moving objects (erythrocytes as well as valve casing and heart walls) its frequency changes - the frequency of ultrasound signal shifts. The greater the velocity of the erythrocytes, the greater the frequency shift of the ultrasound signal. Knowing the frequency of sent ultrasound and the frequency of reflected sound we can determine three important parameters: velocity of the object, which is blood currents, direction of object movement (in this case to the sensor or from the sensor), nature of movement - laminar or turbulent.

The main morphofunctional EchoCG parameters in healthy adolescents are close to those of adults and depend on somatotype. At the age of 15 to 17 years, the diameter of the left ventricular cavity in diastole is 43 to 46 mm, in systole 28 to 32 mm, the left ventricular end-diastolic volume is 106 to 112 ml and systolic volume

is 26 to 30 ml, the right ventricular cavity in diastole varies within 12 to 14 mm, and the left atrium 24 to 26 mm.

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